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Empirical data for the calibration of a model of academia

A collection of empirical data in the literature that helps to calibrate a model of academia.

p-hacking

Gupta, A., & Bosco, F. (2023). Tempest in a teacup: An analysis of p-Hacking in organizational research. *PLOS ONE*, 18(2), e0281938. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0281938>

Johnson, V. E., Payne, R. D., Wang, T., Asher, A., & Mandal, S. (2017). On the reproducibility of psychological science. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 112(517), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.2016.1240079>

Reproducibility

Dreber, A., Pfeiffer, T., Almenberg, J., Isaksson, S., Wilson, B., Chen, Y., Nosek, B. A., & Johannesson, M. (2015). Using prediction markets to estimate the reproducibility of scientific research. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 112(50), 15343–15347. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1516179112>

Replication rate

Makel, M. C., Plucker, J. A., & Hegarty, B. (2012). Replications in psychology research: How often do they really occur? *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 7(6), 537–542. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691612460688>

Base rate of true effects

Wilson, B. M., & Wixted, J. T. (2018). The prior odds of testing a true effect in cognitive and social psychology. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 1(2), 186–197. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245918767122>

Gervais et al. (2015)

- median correct hypothesis rate = 0.6

Gervais, W. M., Jewell, J. A., Najle, M. B., & Ng, B. K. L. (2015). A powerful nudge? Presenting calculable consequences of underpowered research shifts incentives toward adequately powered designs. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 6(7), 847–854. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550615584199>

Gronau et al. (2017)

- “The results indicate that for 41% of the observed p values the H0 assignment probability is larger than .5; this means that, starting from a position of equipoise, for 41% of the observed significant p values it is more likely that they stem from H0 than from H1.”
 - This is conditioned on being significant and published. 60% could be regarded as upper limit for $p(H1)$, though.

Gronau, Q. F., Duizer, M., Bakker, M., & Wagenmakers, E.-J. (2017). Bayesian mixture modeling of significant p values: A meta-analytic method to estimate the degree of contamination from H_0 . *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 146(9), 1223–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000324>

Publication probabilities

Andrews & Kasy (2019)

- 1 for tests that are significant using a two-sided test
- 0.009 for tests that are non-significant using a one-sided test

Andrews, I., & Kasy, M. (2019). Identification of and correction for publication bias. *American Economic Review*, 109(8), 2766–2794. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.20180310>

Fanelli (2012)

Data from Figure 2 for Psychiatry/Psychology (PP) extracted using [WebPlotDigitizer](#).

```
data.frame(  
  year = 1990:2006,  
  positive = c(  
    0.6666666666666666, 0.5555555555555555, 0.8444444444444444,  
    0.7111111111111111,  
    0.82716049382716, 0.9259259259259259300379, 0.760493827160494,  
    0.8666666666666666, 0.85679012345679, 0.874074074074074,  
    0.9382716049382708867199, 1, 0.7851851851851850971897, 1,  
    0.908641975308641,  
    0.9111111111111111, 0.9185185185185180678502  
  )  
)
```

Fanelli, D. (2012). Negative results are disappearing from most disciplines and countries. *Scientometrics*, 90(3), 891–904. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-011-0494-7>

Compatibility of Adrews & Kasy (2019) and Fanelli (2012)

Unter Annahme einer Power von 0.35 kommt man schon recht an den MW von 0.9086, der sich nach Fanelli für die Jahre 2004 bis 2006 ergibt, $\text{sig}(\text{power} = 0.35) = 0.9026$

```
sig <- function(power = 0.35) {  
  # Andrews  
  prob_pub_if_significant <- 1  
  prob_pub_if_not_significant <- .009  
  
  prob_has_true <- 0.09  
  alpha <- 0.05  
  
  hyp <- 1000  
  hyp_true <- hyp * prob_has_true  
  hyp_true_sig <- hyp_true * power  
  hyp_true_sig_pub <- hyp_true_sig * prob_pub_if_significant  
  hyp_true_nsig <- hyp_true * (1-power)  
  hyp_true_nsig_pub <- hyp_true_nsig * prob_pub_if_not_significant  
  
  hyp_ntrue <- hyp * (1-prob_has_true)  
  hyp_ntrue_sig <- hyp_ntrue * alpha  
  hyp_ntrue_sig_pub <- hyp_ntrue_sig * prob_pub_if_significant  
  hyp_ntrue_nsig <- hyp_ntrue * (1-alpha)  
  hyp_ntrue_nsig_pub <- hyp_ntrue_nsig * prob_pub_if_not_significant  
  
  hyp_pub <- hyp_true_sig_pub + hyp_true_nsig_pub + hyp_ntrue_sig_pub +  
  hyp_ntrue_nsig_pub  
  hyp_pub_sig <- hyp_true_sig_pub + hyp_ntrue_sig_pub  
  
  return(hyp_pub_sig/hyp_pub)  
}
```

Typical reported effect sizes

See also: [Advanced Power Analysis](#), pp. 57–63

Richard et al. (2003)

- Distribution of correlation coefficients follows (roughly) a gamma distribution
Richard, F. D., Bond, C. F., & Stokes-Zoota, J. J. (2003). One hundred years of social psychology quantitatively described. *Review of General Psychology*, 7(4), 331–363. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.7.4.331>

Gignac et al. (2016)

- Quartiles of the distribution of correlation coefficients are
 - 25%: 0.11

- 50%: 0.19
- 75%: 0.29

Gignac, G. E., & Szodorai, E. T. (2016). Effect size guidelines for individual differences researchers. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 102, 74–78.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.06.069>

Combining Richard et al. (2003) and Gignac et al. (2016)

Constructing a distribution function of true effect sizes by combining Richard et al. (2003) and Gignac et al. (2016)

- Gamma distribution parameters
 - shape = 2.223179777
 - scale = 0.09759992404
- This approach only takes into account the first and third quartile, but not the second quartile. Maybe a [Metalog distribution](#) could be used as alternative.
- Finding Probability Distribution Parameters from Percentiles:
parameter_percentile.zip

See <https://veryjoe.com/maths/2020/04/27/Parameter-Estimation.html>

Source:

<https://www.codeproject.com/Articles/56371/Finding-Probability-Distribution-Parameters-from-P>

```
gamma_parameters <- function(x1, p1, x2, p2) {
  # Standardize so that x1 < x2 and p1 < p2
  if (p1 > p2) {
    # xor-trick, see https://stackoverflow.com/a/32585867
    p1 <- p1 + p2
    p2 <- p1 - p2
    p1 <- p1 - p2

    x1 <- x1 + x2
    x2 <- x1 - x2
    x1 <- x1 - x2
  }
}
```

```
objective <- function(shape) {
  qgamma(p2, shape) / qgamma(p1, shape) - x2/x1
}
```

The objective function we're wanting to find a root of is decreasing.
 # We need to find an interval over which it goes from positive to negative.

```
left <- right <- 1.0
```

```
while (objective(left) < 0.0) {
  left <- left / 2
}
while(objective(right) > 0.0) {
```

```

    right <- right * 2
  }

  shape <- pracma::bisect(objective, left, right)$root
  scale <- x1 / qgamma(p1, shape)

  list(shape = shape, scale = scale)
}

# Use the quantiles from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.06.069>...
corr_vals <- c(0.11, 0.19, 0.29)
# ...to construct a gamma distribution as found at
# <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.7.4.331>.
gamma_parameters(corr_vals[1], 0.25, corr_vals[3], 0.75)

# $shape
# [1] 2.223179777
#
# $scale
# [1] 0.09759992404

# Then, draw from this distribution of correlation coefficients, convert to
# Cohen's d and halve it because published effects are overestimating true
# effects.
truncdist::rtrunc(n = 10,
                  spec = "gamma",
                  a = 0.0,
                  b = 1.0,
                  shape = 2.223179777,
                  scale = 0.09759992404) |>
  (\(r) 2 * r / sqrt(1 - r^2))() |>
  (\(d) d/2)()

sessionInfo()

# R version 4.2.1 (2022-06-23)
# Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
# Running under: Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS
#
# Matrix products: default
# BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas/libblas.so.3
# LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libopenblas-r0.2.20.so
#
# locale:
# [1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_NUMERIC=C
LC_TIME=en_US.UTF-8
# [4] LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_MONETARY=en_US.UTF-8

```

```

LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8
# [7] LC_PAPER=en_US.UTF-8          LC_NAME=C          LC_ADDRESS=C
# [10] LC_TELEPHONE=C                LC_MEASUREMENT=en_US.UTF-8
LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
#
# attached base packages:
# [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods   base
#
# Loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
# [1] compiler_4.2.1 magrittr_2.0.3 cli_3.4.1    tools_4.2.1
rstudioapi_0.14 crayon_1.5.2
# [7] colorDF_0.1.7  rlang_1.0.6   pracma_2.4.2 purrr_0.3.5

```

Sample sizes

Carter et al. (2019)

- Distribution of sample sizes follows an inverse gamma distribution with a shape of 1.153 and scale of 0.046, truncated at $n = 5$ and $n = 1905$.

Carter, E. C., Schönbrodt, F. D., Gervais, W. M., & Hilgard, J. (2019). Correcting for bias in psychology: A comparison of meta-analytic methods. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 2(2), 115–144.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245919847196>

Fraley et al. (2022)

- `weighted_mean` = 1.132489 (before correction) or 1.128781 (after correction)
- `n_years` = 2019L - 2011L
- `n_pact_factor` = $\text{weighted_mean}^{(n_years-1L)}$
 – `n_pact_factor` == 2.38912 (before correction) or 2.334893 (after correction)

```

library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(ggplot2)

```

```

data.frame(
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE,
  Journal = c("JRP", "EJP", "JP", "PSPB",
             "PS:S", "SPPS", "JPSP", "EJSP", "JESP"),
  Aggregate.NF = c(330L, 261L, 251L, 200L, 200L, 186L, 179L, 131L, 113L),
  NF.2011 = c("238 (17)", "111 (13)",
            "239 (14)", "105 (51)", "72 (26)", "128 (26)", "98 (70)",
            "96 (31)", "94 (66)"),
  NF.2012 = c("438 (14)", "194 (16)",
            "198 (22)", "78 (47)", "82 (24)", "134 (24)", "108 (75)",
            "93 (29)", "69 (53)"),
  NF.2013 = c("325 (26)", "392 (14)",
            "354 (16)", "117 (50)", "174 (20)", "210 (25)", "102 (73)",
            "78 (24)", "120 (68)"),

```

```

NF.2014 = c("302 (15)", "217 (7)",
            "359 (10)", "151 (62)", "104 (21)", "172 (26)", "116 (71)",
            "139 (29)", "92 (56)"),
NF.2015 = c("369 (14)", "200 (12)",
            "406 (19)", "200 (36)", "200 (36)", "186 (38)", "220 (64)",
            "131 (34)", "113 (89)"),
NF.2016 = c("280 (11)", "261 (15)",
            "239 (23)", "231 (35)", "231 (35)", "178 (29)", "179 (81)",
            "126 (30)", "102 (46)"),
NF.2017 = c("330 (18)", "422 (15)",
            "251 (11)", "248 (23)", "248 (23)", "300 (39)", "225 (77)",
            "219 (27)", "204 (60)"),
NF.2018 = c("500 (20)", "576 (11)",
            "240 (44)", "386 (52)", "386 (52)", "364 (26)", "225 (75)",
            "153 (42)", "206 (81)"),
NF.2019 = c("438 (22)", "496 (10)",
            "286 (30)", "202 (32)", "202 (32)", "383 (33)", "320 (45)",
            "169 (60)", "275 (70)")
) -> raw_data_before_correction

data.frame(
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE,
  Journal = c("JRP", "EJP", "JP", "PS:S",
             "SPPS", "JPSP", "PSPB", "EJSP", "JESP"),
  Aggregate.NF = c(330L, 261L, 251L, 200L, 186L, 179L, 139L, 131L, 113L),
  NF.2011 = c("238 (17)", "111 (13)",
             "239 (14)", "72 (26)", "128 (26)", "98 (70)", "105 (51)",
             "96 (31)", "94 (66)"),
  NF.2012 = c("438 (14)", "194 (16)",
             "198 (22)", "82 (24)", "134 (24)", "108 (75)", "78 (47)",
             "93 (29)", "69 (53)"),
  NF.2013 = c("325 (26)", "392 (14)",
             "354 (16)", "174 (20)", "210 (25)", "102 (73)", "117 (50)",
             "78 (24)", "120 (68)"),
  NF.2014 = c("302 (15)", "217 (7)",
             "359 (10)", "104 (21)", "172 (26)", "116 (71)", "151 (62)",
             "139 (29)", "92 (56)"),
  NF.2015 = c("369 (14)", "200 (12)",
             "406 (19)", "200 (36)", "186 (38)", "220 (64)", "130 (84)",
             "131 (34)", "113 (89)"),
  NF.2016 = c("280 (11)", "261 (15)",
             "239 (23)", "231 (35)", "178 (29)", "179 (81)", "139 (57)",
             "126 (30)", "102 (46)"),
  NF.2017 = c("330 (18)", "422 (15)",
             "251 (11)", "248 (23)", "300 (39)", "225 (77)", "186 (74)",
             "219 (27)", "204 (60)"),
  NF.2018 = c("500 (20)", "576 (11)",
             "240 (44)", "386 (52)", "364 (26)", "225 (75)", "220 (51)",
             "153 (42)", "206 (81)"),
  NF.2019 = c("438 (22)", "496 (10)",
             "286 (30)", "202 (32)", "202 (32)", "383 (33)", "320 (45)",
             "169 (60)", "275 (70)")
)

```

```

      "286 (30)", "202 (32)", "383 (33)", "320 (45)", "208 (51)",
      "169 (60)", "275 (70)")
) -> raw_data_after_correction

# Extract medians
medians <- raw_data_after_correction %>%
  select(-c(Aggregate.NF)) %>%
  mutate(across(starts_with("NF."), \(x) x |> substring(first = 1, last = 3)
|> trimws() |> as.integer()))

# see https://datascience.stackexchange.com/a/75258
medians_stats <- medians %>%
  pivot_longer(-c(Journal), names_to = "year", names_prefix = "NF.",
names_transform = as.integer) %>%
  arrange(Journal, year) %>%
  group_by(Journal) %>%
  mutate(lag = lag(value), # Create a dummy column
'lag'
         Previous = value / lag, # Calculate RateOfChange
         First = head(value, 1), # Dummy column for the
first yearly value by group
         Baseline = value / First) %>% # Calculate
BaselineChange
  select(Journal, year, value, # Select only columns
you want
         Previous, Baseline)

# Plot data
medians_stats |>
  ggplot(aes(x = year, y = Previous, color = Journal)) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm", se = FALSE)

# Calculate linear fits
# see https://stackoverflow.com/a/30163784
medians_stats %>%
  group_by(Journal) %>%
  do({
    mod = lm(formula = value ~ year, data = .)
    data.frame(Intercept = coef(mod)[1],
              Slope = coef(mod)[2])
  })

# Calculate mean change
medians_stats %>%
  group_by(Journal) %>%
  summarise(m = mean(Previous, na.rm = TRUE)) %>%
  getElement("m") %>%

```

```

mean() -> unweighted_mean

# Extract weights
weights <- raw_data_after_correction %>%
  select(-c(Aggregate.NF)) %>%
  mutate(across(starts_with("NF."), \(x) x |> substring(first = nchar(x) -
2L, last = nchar(x) - 1L) |> gsub(pattern = "(", fixed = TRUE, replacement =
"")) |> as.integer()))

weights_stats <- purrr::map2(medians |> select(-c(Journal)),
  weights |> select(-c(Journal)),
  weighted.mean) %>%
  as.data.frame() %>%
  pivot_longer(everything(), names_to = "year", names_prefix = "NF.",
names_transform = as.integer) %>%
  mutate(lag = lag(value), # Create a dummy column
'lag'
  Previous = value / lag, # Calculate RateOfChange
  First = head(value, 1), # Dummy column for the
first yearly value by group
  Baseline = value / First) %>% # Calculate
BaselineChange
  select(year, value, # Select only columns you want
  Previous, Baseline)

# Calculate mean change
weights_stats %>%
  getElement("Previous") %>%
  mean(na.rm = TRUE) -> weighted_mean

sessionInfo()

# R version 4.2.1 (2022-06-23)
# Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)
# Running under: Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS
#
# Matrix products: default
# BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas/libblas.so.3
# LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libopenblas-r0.2.20.so
#
# Locale:
# [1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_NUMERIC=C
LC_TIME=en_US.UTF-8
# [4] LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_MONETARY=en_US.UTF-8
LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8
# [7] LC_PAPER=en_US.UTF-8 LC_NAME=C LC_ADDRESS=C
# [10] LC_TELEPHONE=C LC_MEASUREMENT=en_US.UTF-8
LC_IDENTIFICATION=C
#

```

```

# attached base packages:
# [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets  methods   base
#
# other attached packages:
# [1] ggplot2_3.3.6 tidyr_1.2.1  dplyr_1.0.10
#
# Loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
# [1] rstudioapi_0.14 magrittr_2.0.3  munsell_0.5.0  tidyselect_1.2.0
colorspace_2.0-3 colorDF_0.1.7
# [7] R6_2.5.1          rlang_1.0.6     fansi_1.0.3    tools_4.2.1
grid_4.2.1         gtable_0.3.1
# [13] utf8_1.2.2        cli_3.4.1       DBI_1.1.3      withr_2.5.0
ellipsis_0.3.2    assertthat_0.2.1
# [19] tibble_3.1.8     lifecycle_1.0.3 crayon_1.5.2   purrr_0.3.5
vctrs_0.4.2       glue_1.6.2
# [25] compiler_4.2.1  pillar_1.8.1    scales_1.2.1   generics_0.1.3
pkgconfig_2.0.3

```

Fraley, R. C., Chong, J. Y., Baacke, K. A., Greco, A. J., Guan, H., & Vazire, S. (2022). Journal n-pact factors from 2011 to 2019: Evaluating the quality of social/personality journals with respect to sample size and statistical power. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 5(4), 251524592211202. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459221120217>

Corrigendum: Journal n-pact factors from 2011 to 2019: evaluating the quality of social/personality journals with respect to sample size and statistical power. (2023). *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 6(2), 251524592311750. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459231175075>

Schäfer et al. (2019)

- studies without pre-registration: Mdn = 89
- studies with pre-registration: Mdn = 267

Schäfer, T., & Schwarz, M. A. (2019). The meaningfulness of effect sizes in psychological research: Differences between sub-disciplines and the impact of potential biases. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 813. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00813>

Openness

Piwowar, H., Priem, J., Larivière, V., Alperin, J. P., Matthias, L., Norlander, B., Farley, A., West, J., & Haustein, S. (2018). The state of OA: A large-scale analysis of the prevalence and impact of Open Access articles. *PeerJ*, 6, e4375. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4375>

Errors

Nuijten et al., 2015

- $1.6\% / 10.6\% = 15\%$ of all articles with inconsistencies had inconsistencies that affected the statistical conclusion.

Reporting inconsistencies are presented both at the level of article and at the level of the individual p-value, i.e., the percentage of articles with at least one inconsistency and the average percentage of p-values within an article that is inconsistent, respectively.

Across all journals and years 49.6 % of the articles with NHST results contained at least one inconsistency (8,273 of the 16,695 articles) and 12.9 % (2,150) of the articles with NHST results contained at least one gross inconsistency.

Furthermore, overall 9.7 % (24,961) of the p-values were inconsistent, and 1.4 % (3,581) of the p-values were grossly inconsistent. We also calculated the percentage of inconsistencies per article and averaged these percentages over all articles. We call this the “(gross) inconsistency rate”. Across journals, the inconsistency rate was 10.6 % and the gross inconsistency rate was 1.6 %.

Nuijten, M. B., Hartgerink, C. H. J., van Assen, M. A. L. M., Epskamp, S., & Wicherts, J. M. (2016). The prevalence of statistical reporting errors in psychology (1985–2013). *Behavior Research Methods*, 48(4), 1205–1226.
<https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-015-0664-2>

Reproducibility

Stodden et al., 2018

- Looks at no specific field (articles published in journal *Science*).
- $1 - (26\% / 44\%) = 41\%$ (37) of articles with available data (90) could not be reproduced.

We found that we were able to obtain artifacts from 44% of our sample and were able to reproduce the findings for 26%.

Stodden, V., Seiler, J., & Ma, Z. (2018). An empirical analysis of journal policy effectiveness for computational reproducibility. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(11), 2584–2589.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1708290115>

Hardwicke et al., 2018

- Looks at papers published in subfield of psychology (articles published in journal *Cognition*).
- 37% (13) of articles with available data (35) could not be reproduced.

For 13 articles [37%] at least one value could not be reproduced despite author assistance.

Hardwicke, T. E., Mathur, M. B., MacDonald, K., Nilsson, G., Banks, G. C., Kidwell, M. C., Hofelich Mohr, A., Clayton, E., Yoon, E. J., Henry Tessler, M., Lenne, R. L., Altman, S., Long, B., & Frank, M. C. (2018). Data availability, reusability, and analytic reproducibility: Evaluating the impact of a mandatory open data policy at the journal *Cognition*. *Royal Society Open Science*, 5(8), 180448. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.180448>

Obels et al., 2020

- Looks at registered reports in psychology.
- $21/36 = 58\%$ (21) of articles with available data (36) could not be reproduced.

Both data and code for 36 of the articles were shared. We could run the scripts for 31 analyses, and we reproduced the main results for 21 articles. Although the percentage of articles for which both data and code were shared (36 out of 62, or 58%) and the percentage of articles for which main results could be computationally reproduced (21 out of 36, or 58%) were relatively high compared with the percentages found in other studies, there is clear room for improvement.

Obels, P., Lakens, D., Coles, N. A., Gottfried, J., & Green, S. A. (2020). Analysis of open data and computational reproducibility in registered reports in psychology. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 3(2), 229–237. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515245920918872>

Naudet et al., 2018

- Looks at randomized controlled trials in biomedicine (articles published in journals *The BMJ* and *PLOS Medicine*).
- $100\% - 82\% = 18\%$ (3) of articles with available data (17) could not be reproduced.

17/37 (46%, 95% confidence interval 30% to 62%) satisfied the definition of data availability and 14 of the 17 (82%, 59% to 94%) were fully reproduced on all their primary outcomes.

Naudet, F., Sakarovitch, C., Janiaud, P., Cristea, I., Fanelli, D., Moher, D., & Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2018). Data sharing and reanalysis of randomized controlled trials in leading biomedical journals with a full data sharing policy: Survey of studies published in *The BMJ* and *PLOS Medicine*. *BMJ*, k400. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.k400>

Hardwicke et al., 2021

- Looks at articles with open data badges in psychology (articles published in journal *Psychological Science*).
- $12\% + 28\% = 40\%$ (10) of articles with available data (25) could not be reproduced.

not fully reproducible with no substantive author response for 3 (12% [0,35]) articles; and not fully reproducible despite author involvement for 7 (28% [12,51]) articles

Hardwicke, T. E., Bohn, M., MacDonald, K., Hembacher, E., Nuijten, M. B., Peloquin, B. N., deMayo, B. E., Long, B., Yoon, E. J., & Frank, M. C. (2021). Analytic

reproducibility in articles receiving open data badges at the journal Psychological Science: An observational study. Royal Society Open Science, 8(1), 201494.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.201494>

Combining Stodden et al. (2018), Hardwicke et al. (2018), Obels et al. (2020) and Hardwicke et al. (2021)

- This combination makes a lot of assumptions that do not hold (but we hope that breaking them is not too critical):
 - articles are from the same field
 - data and code were available for all analyzed papers
- 45% of articles with available data can not be reproduced, on average.

```
vals <- c(0.41, 0.37, 0.58, 0.4)
weights <- c(37, 13, 21, 10)
```

```
weighted.mean(vals, weights)
```

Combining research on statistical errors (Nuijten et al., 2015) with research on reproducibility (Stodden et al., 2018; Hardwicke et al., 2018; Obels et al., 2020; Hardwicke et al., 2021)

- 45% of articles with available data can not be reproduced.
 - 15% of articles with inconsistencies had gross inconsistencies (“gross rate”).
 - This can be applied to the reproducibility of articles with available data if: (1) the gross rate is the same for statistical reporting errors and for programming errors and (2) the gross rate is the same for papers with unavailable data and for papers with available data.
 - Then 15% of articles which can not be (exactly) reproduced show results so different that they lead to different conclusions.
- Articles without available data cannot be reproduced.

Whether an article has available data depends on its openness and its authors:

- x% of articles have data(+code) available without requesting them from authors.
- y% of articles have data(+code) available after requesting them from authors.
- z% of articles have data(+code) not available.

This model neglects, however, that articles with data shared in advance might have a higher (computational) reproducibility because of selection effects (e.g. “I share my data if I am confident in the results.”). If this were the case, less than 45% of articles with available data that needed to be requested can be reproduced. But we need only consider this if a reproduction of non-open papers is a possibility at all.

Prevalence of QRPs

- 0.05286031
- extracted with [WebPlotDigitizer](#) from figure 2

Fiedler, K., & Schwarz, N. (2016). Questionable research practices revisited. *Social Psychological and Personality Science*, 7(1), 45–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550615612150>

```
qrp_data <- data.frame(  
  qrp = c(  
    "QRP0", "QRP1", "QRP2", "QRP3", "QRP4", "QRP5", "QRP6", "QRP7",  
    "QRP8", "QRP9"  
  ),  
  prevalence2 = c(  
    0.079822261640798223034654, 0.05853658536585352317738,  
    0.04789356984478931877902, 0.008869179600886871114862,  
    0.0407982226164079791356, 0.1082039911308203261608,  
    0.07627494456762741459332,  
    0.1011086474501108195545, 0.00532150776053204235122,  
    0.001773835920177347378127  
  )  
)  
  
mean(qrp_data$prevalence2)
```